

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880727>

DISCLOSURE OF INTERSUBJECT CONNECTIONS USING APPLIED TASKS.

Opaeva G.A,

Opaeva Gulbakhar Aymanovna-Senior lecturer at the Department of Functional Analysis, Algebra and Geometry, Karakalpak State University

Kalbaeva G.M

Qalbaeva Guldana Madiyarovna-Schoolgirl of #1 st school

Abstract. *The interdisciplinary connection between mathematics and physics at the level of activities can be realized through the methods of scientific cognition. Both mathematics and physics use such methods as observation, comparison, analogy, induction, deduction, analysis, synthesis, generalization, concretization, abstraction, specialization. This article presents a task demonstrating the implementation of interdisciplinary connections at the level of activities, through the method of analogy.*

Keywords. *Intersubject relations, model, interpretation.*

Interdisciplinary connections can be carried out not only at the level of knowledge, but also at the level of activities. In mathematics, various activities are used in the learning process. For example, a type of activity is used: to compose a text task according to a given equation. A similar type of activity can be applied in the process of teaching physics [1].

Task (physical). The body is thrown up with some initial velocity. After how long will it reach this height?

Solution. Let's consider this problem as an applied one and find its solution according to a three-stage scheme.

Step I. Formalization. Let's build a mathematical model of the problem. At the same time, we use the knowledge of students obtained in the physics course. The height of lifting the body is affected by the speed at which the throw is performed: the higher the speed of throwing, the higher height the body will reach. Denote by V_0 (m/s) - the initial speed of throwing the body, after h (m)-the height that the body should reach, after t (s)-the time after which the body will be at height h . Drawing on the knowledge of students from the physics course that the movement of a body thrown vertically upwards is equidistant, we find an expression for height h : , here g (m/c²)-acceleration of the body's free fall. The mathematical model is constructed.

Step II. Solving the problem within the framework of the built model. This solution boils down to finding t from the equation: $h = v_0 t - \frac{gt^2}{2}$. Let's convert the equation to the form: $gt^2 - 2v_0 t + 2h = 0$.

We get the square value with respect to t equation, discriminant D which is equal to:

Cases may arise:

1. $D < 0$, i.e. $0 < v_0^2 < 2gh$, . The equation has no solutions.
2. $D = 0$, i.e. . In this case, the equation has one solution .
3. $D > 0$, i.e. . In this case, the equation has two roots: and .

The problem is solved within the framework of the constructed model.

Step III. Interpretation. Let's translate the result into the language of the original problem.

- If $D < 0$, then the equation is unsolvable. This means that the body at the initial velocity doesn't reach the height h .
- If $D = 0$ and the equation has a unique solution and this means that the body will reach a height of h in seconds.
- If $D > 0$, i.e., the equation has two solutions t_1 and t_2 , and from the point of view of physics, this means that the body will reach a height of h twice: going up in seconds and going down in seconds.

Intersubject connections in this task, as well as in the previous one, are revealed at the level of knowledge. Solving this problem, as well as in the previous one, helps the student's mathematical development. The teacher takes care of the student's mathematical development first, because many of the facts learned at school will eventually be forgotten, and the student's mathematical development will remain forever. Mathematical development involves the development of strong thinking skills of the student. In the process of finding a solution to this problem, many of these skills are formed and further developed. By myself the main mental operation, in our opinion, is here the operation of abstraction. We single out the ability to abstract because the main method of mathematics is abstraction. Only by distracting ourselves from certain aspects of reality do we reveal the mathematical mechanism of the phenomena and processes under study. Such a distraction requires drawing up a mathematical model as the law of motion of a body thrown vertically upwards. It also shows such a feature of mental activity as the ability to schematize, the ability to move from a specific statement of the question to the scheme. At the same time, it is important for students to make sure that this scheme contains only what is needed to solve a mathematical problem. The study of the solvability of the obtained quadratic equation depending on the value of the discriminant of the equation requires a lot of

thought effort. Ability to analyze the situation, isolate special cases ($D>0$, $D=0$, $D<0$) and get the right conclusions based on this analysis – this skill is one of the most valuable thinking skills that we strive to develop in a student. This skill contributes to the development of such qualities of mathematical thinking as criticality, depth, and flexibility. At the stage of interpretation, flexibility of thinking is required, since two values of the variable are obtained and this ambiguity requires the ability to go beyond the boundaries of the usual method of action, the ability to rebuild the system of acquired knowledge as new knowledge is acquired and experience is accumulated.

The solution of the applied problem consists of three stages. The most important and complex stage is the first stage – the construction of the mathematical model itself. It is carried out in a logical way based on a deep analysis of the process or phenomenon under study. It requires the ability to describe the process or phenomenon in mathematical language. Ideally, we want to build a mathematical model that is adequate to the original prototype. In fact, adequacy is not achieved, because it is impossible to take into account and express in the language of mathematics all the factors that affect this process or phenomenon. Therefore, the mathematical model only approximately reflects the phenomenon under consideration. The more reliable the simulation results are, the smaller the error allowed when compiling the model.

When solving applied problems, the following terminology is also used: external mathematical modeling and internal mathematical modeling.

In external mathematical modeling, there is a distraction from the characteristics and properties of real objects and a mental transition to ideal, abstract objects, such as mathematical objects. This transition is possible only when the ability to generalize is developed, to move from the individual to the general, to distract from properties that are not essential for a given real object in favor of those properties that are necessary for this object and distinguish it from other objects. By inviting students to make such a transition, we are helping them to develop their own skills. the corresponding qualities of thinking. At the same time, we assume that the main emphasis in teaching is not on memorizing educational information, but on its deep understanding, on developing students' skills to creatively apply this information in practice. Since the development of mathematical thinking is closely related to the formation of thinking techniques in educational activities (these techniques are analysis, synthesis, generalization, abstraction, etc. If these techniques are most clearly and successfully manifested in problem solving, then it becomes possible to make the development of students' thinking a controlled process, using tasks that require external mathematical and internal mathematical modeling[3].

Since the systematic study of algebra and physics begins simultaneously, it becomes possible to study them in close relationship. Knowledge of physical laws contributes to understanding the meaning of mathematical concepts, and, conversely, mathematical knowledge is consolidated in the study of physics. This relationship is best realized in the process of solving applied problems[4].

In addition, the following approach significantly activates students 'thinking and attracts them to the study of mathematics: fill the abstract, abstract condition of a mathematical problem with practical content that helps the teacher to arouse students' creative search, and will activate their thinking[5].

References

1. Zorina L. Ya. Intersubject relations as a basis for forming the scientific worldview of schoolchildren / Intersubject relations in the process of teaching the basics of science in secondary schools. Edited by I. D. Zverev, Moscow, 1972, pp. 26-31.
2. Fedorova V. N., Kiryushkin D. M. Intersubject relations. On the material of natural-scientific disciplines of secondary school, Moscow: Pedagogika Publ., 1972, 152 p.
3. Usova A.V. Intersubject relations as a necessary didactic condition for improving the scientific level of teaching the basics of science at school// Intersubject relations of teaching the basics of science at school. Chelyabinsk, 1973, issue 1, pp. 23-38.
4. Intersubject and intrasubject communications as a reserve for improving the effectiveness of training. Moscow: Research Institute of SIMO APN of the USSR, 1975. 132 p.
5. Балтабаева Р. Б., Бекназаров М. К., Курбанова А. Х. РАСКРЫТИЕ МЕЖПРЕДМЕТНЫХ СВЯЗЕЙ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ПРИКЛАДНЫХ ЗАДАЧ //Academy. – 2021. – №. 6 (69). – С. 57-59.